

EDUCATIONAL METHODS AND INNOVATION IN PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY THE ROLE AND ADVANTAGES OF THE METHODS AND THE ORGANIZATION OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS BASED ON THE TECHNOLOGY OF COOPERATION

Samatova Sanobar Nazarovna

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Abstract. Educational methods and innovation in pedagogical activity in these article effective aspects of the use of methods, in this process, between disciplines state of integration, when creating innovative techniques, Information Communication the possibilities of technologies are presented. The article also shows the factors of ensuring high achievement using collaborative technology, developing the educational and educational motives of the student, as well as implementing the principles of humanization of the educational process.

Key words: method, innovation, innovative activity, innovative environment, technology, pedagogical innovation, integration, quality, effective collaborative training, socio-psychological environment, collaborative relations, education, team training, small group training, independent thinking.

МЕТОДЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ И ИННОВАЦИИ В ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ РОЛЬ И ПРЕИМУЩЕСТВА МЕТОДОВ И ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОГО ПРОЦЕССА, ОСНОВАННЫХ НА ТЕХНОЛОГИИ СОТРУДНИЧЕСТВА

Аннотация. Образовательные методы и инновации в педагогической деятельности в данной статье рассматриваются эффективные аспекты использования методов в этом процессе, состояние интеграции между дисциплинами, при создании инновационных методик, информационной коммуникации, представлены возможности технологий. В статье также показаны факторы обеспечения высоких достижений с использованием коллаборативных технологий, развития образовательных и воспитательных мотивов студента, а также реализации принципов гуманизации образовательного процесса.

Ключевые слова: метод, инновация, инновационная деятельность, инновационная среда, технология, педагогическая инновация, интеграция, качество, эффективное совместное обучение, социально-психологическая среда, отношения сотрудничества, образование, командное обучение, обучение в малых группах, независимое мышление.

INTRODUCTION

The most important and central issue of pedagogical innovation activity is educational it consists in the effective and high-quality organization of the process. There are different methods of teaching, namely methods. The teacher is looking for an opportunity to achieve the goal of teaching in whatever style, in this regard, from educational methods and innovative methods uses. Educational methods have shown their effectiveness by this time teachers of the time are coming and trying to get better results by taking classes in a new style. Also using innovative techniques agree. Pedagogical innovations in innovative activities: the creation and application of new methods and techniques of teaching creates an effective and high-quality organization of the educational process. Pedagogical innovation is a factor in the enrichment and development of

theory and practice of education and upbringing by introducing changes in pedagogical activity that were previously unknown in the educational process.

As well as modern pedagogical technologies of the educational process increases the effectiveness, forms the free thinking process of students, increases the passion and pleasure of learning in students, strengthens their knowledge mastering, skills and qualifications of their independent use in practice forms.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

"Method" is derived from the Greek "metodos" - "way", which means means research. Educational method teacher in the educational process and it is a joint activity aimed at the achievement of a specific goal by students. Educational methods-achieving the goal of teaching itself denotes methods and ways of theoretical and practical orientation of educational material. Teaching methods educational process of educational and educational activities how it should be, how to organize and conduct the training process and what kind of work and actions are performed by those who receive education in this process determines the need. Also educational method teacher and education theoretical and practical knowledge aimed at performing the reading tasks of the recipients the way of activity. Educational methods general knowledge of the world around it depends on the understanding of their laws, that is, they have a philosophical methodological basis and understand the contradictions in the educational process, the essence of the educational process and the result of a correct understanding of its principles. Educational material in the content of Education it depends on the logic of expressed scientific thought. How much is Theory in pedagogical views underrepresented, the less educational methods will depend on this theory.

Pedagogical science provides advanced work experiences of schools and educators summarizes, shows the scientific foundations of traditional education, helps to creatively track down modern and effective teaching methods. Methods consist of a number of main groups, each of which, in turn, is divided into subgroups and individual methods included in them. Taking into account the fact that the process of organizing and carrying out educational activities itself implies the transfer of information, acceptance, awareness and memorization of educational information, and the ability to apply the knowledge and skills acquired in practice, methods of transmitting information by word to the methods of the first group and receiving it by hearing oral methods; Story, Lecture, conversation, etc.; methods of receiving educational information by visual transmission and vision to the methods of the second group — visual methods: imaging, demonstration, etc.; for giving educational information to the methods of the Working Group through practical labor actions (practical methods, exercises, laboratory experiments, labor enters. Hence, the following educational methods that are widely used in practice can be expressed in terms of Considering the provision of knowledge and skills to be able to apply in practice, methods of the first group include methods of transmitting information by word and receiving it by hearing oral methods; Story, Lecture, conversation, etc.; methods of the second group include methods of receiving educational information by visual transmission and vision — visual methods: pictorial, demonstration, etc.; methods of the Working Group give educational information through practical labor actions (practical methods, exercises, laboratory experiments, labor movements, etc.). Hence, the educational methods that are widely used in practice can be expressed in the following way. Educational methods consist of study methods and teaching methods. When the teacher verbally states knowledge, the children listen to it. Teacher independent if the job is submitted, the students will perform. In the educational process, a complex of teaching and reading methods is used in order to increase the effectiveness of educational methods. In the didactic views of Eastern thinkers, too, serious attention is paid to the issue of educational methods. This can be clearly noticed by Al-Khwarazmiy, Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Rayhan Beruniy, Abu Ali ibn Sina's views on various educational methods, views, directions of Education practiced. Muhammad ibn Musa al-Khwarazmiy tried to synthesize the methods of education that had existed before him. Abu Rayhan Beruni's views on ways, methods of acquiring scientific knowledge are also relevant for the current period. In his opinion, the following should be considered when teaching learners:

- not boring the educated;
- when giving knowledge, it is imperative not to teach the same thing or science, this is one of the requirements for the lesson schedule;
- Continuity and consistency;
- Taxation and comparison;
- Repeat;
- A visual statement of the material, and so on.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The educational method has a psychological basis. The child's age opportunities in mastering educational material and his level of maturity have a huge impact on teaching and reading methods. A good knowledge of the thinking activities and personal characteristics of educators gives an opportunity to find more effective ways of teaching. In the process of education on the concept of personal activity of training specialists, it is necessary to look at the process of

individual education as a process of formation of an individual-creative personality, as well as to make training not only taught

it is considered that science allows you to organize in accordance with the logic of the development of the individual, and not with the logic of the individual. The creative (creative potentiation) ability of the learner guarantees the fulfillment of the order of a social Society (information technology industry, information educational documents, users) by building an informed society in improving efficiency and quality at all stages of the educational process, its ability to make an announcement, the culture of learning, the achievement of promising results in choosing optimal options for the development In this, an active educational process is carried out. Active education consists of a systematic pedagogical process that ensures the conscious and active participation, independence and creative abilities of the educator and educator in the educational process. In the context of active education, the acquired methods of knowledge and action will be perfectly systematic in content, logically complete and suitable for use in various production situations. The following educational methods are mainly used in this: controversy; involvement in thinking; strengthening on the board; introduction into practice of various educational and professional games, etc. Activation of educational methods requires increased attention to the following educational laws. As you know today in the course of the lesson-Crossword", - icebreaking, —Synkveill, —Case study, —Insert, —BBB, —Vein diagram, —brainstorming, and —zig-zag technologies used in the educational process.

In this article, we recommend several more innovative techniques that serve to ensure the effectiveness and quality of the course process. Some non-traditional that collaborative teaching technologies implement lesson forms Press conference lesson-the topic of the lesson through question answers mastering exercise. Cheerful, witty club lesson-an interesting question-by finding answers to their exercise to teach independent thinking. A group work lesson is an exercise in strengthening knowledge by organizing students to perform tasks in multiple groups. A cross-teaching lesson is a lesson in mastering a topic by arranging for students to explain to each other some paragraphs or similar small fragments of the text on the content of the lesson. The lesson that students take is the exercise of increasing student activity by arranging for the topic of the lesson to be explained by students.

-Competitive lesson-on one or more topics of students in the classroom.

- Organization of a pre-arranged competition, a lesson to determine the winners. Working in pairs (binary) lesson-a lesson in which students are in pairs and teach the topic of the lesson a lesson to master together or consolidate each other's knowledge. Couples can be changed differently during the course of the lesson when necessary in this. Dialogue lesson-consists of exercises to explain and strengthen the topic of the lesson by organizing dialogues with students in order to teach students to think independently and develop skills to express their thoughts. An exercise lesson in a circle consists of exercises to master a new topic based on the alternating participation of students or to consolidate, repeating the lesson mentioned.

The innovation lesson is a lesson in introducing innovations related to the field of educational science or school life, as well as introducing imitations and projects on the practical application of the results of students 'creative activities, which serves to improve students' knowledge, develop their creative abilities.

The main idea of collaborative teaching: study assignments not only together to perform, but also to study in collaboration.

Collaborative teaching provides for the formation of the following in the student:

Daily intense mental work of every reader, creative and independent thought teaching to keep;

Awareness as a person, education of independence;

Creating a sense of personal worth in every reader;

Strengthening the confidence of a person in his power and ability;

The formation of a sense of responsibility in the education of a student. The technology of collaborative teaching is in the study of each student with the realization that their success would lead to the success of the band, the regular and from diligence to mental work, to complete and high-quality training assignments, to thoroughly master the educational material, to partner with his comrades, among themselves help prepares the ground for organizing.

Collaborative training of students in collaborative learning technology there are several methods of organization:

1. Command Training (R.Slavin).

2. Collaborative training in small groups (R.Slavin, 1986).

3. The “zigzag or saw” method of collaborative teaching (E.Aronson, 1978).

4. The “read together” method of collaborative teaching (University of Minnesota professors R.Johnson, D.Johnson, 1987).

5. Method of organizing creative search in small groups (Tel Aviv in Israel University professor Sh.Developed by Sharan1988).

Command Training (R.Slavin)

When training in a team, learners are allocated to two teams with equal numbers. Both teams perform the same assignment. Team members receive training assignments by doing it in collaboration, each student has the knowledge, skills and knowledge provided for in the subject focuses on Skill Acquisition. R.Slavin argues that it is not enough for students to be instructed to carry out assignments cooperatively. It is necessary for a literal cooperation between students, the joy of the success achieved by each student, the feeling of helping each other diligently, the emergence of a favorable socio-psychological environment. In this technology, when determining the quality of students' mastery of knowledge, they are compared not with each other, but with the result that each student's daily result was obtained earlier.

Only then do students feel responsible, realizing that the result they have achieved during the course of the lesson will benefit the team, seeking to seek more, to thoroughly master knowledge, skills and competencies.

Collaborative training in small groups

In this method, subgroups are made up of 4 students. The teacher first explains the topic, and then organizes the independent work of students.

Training assignments are divided into four parts, with each student completing a specific part of the assignment. At the end of the assignment, each student reflects on the part he or she has completed and trains his or her comrades, and then a general conclusion is drawn on the assignment by the team members. The teacher listens to each small group of information and assesses the knowledge in control using test questions. In cooperation, specific pedagogical, psychological and

methodological foundations for the effective use of teaching technologies have been developed, which are as follows:

- Organizational and pedagogical foundations - educational plan, program, lesson topic, DTS requirements and based on the volume of new knowledge that is required to be mastered at the level in accordance with them

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, I can say that the information communication system is huge in an era of development at the level, educators have developed techniques and technology knowledgeable and skilled at the level of deep knowledge, analysis and innovation must be. For this, all knowledge in the process of organizing the lesson able to choose and apply soda, understandable and easy-to-use methods to buyers, the use of visual weapons, correct from pedagogical technologies and I think it is advisable to use it effectively. The purpose of collaborative learning activities is to create a control mechanism for the acquired activity and joint actions, attitudes and communication. The product of collaborative activities is the emergence of new ideas that students put forward and goals that depend on the essence of the activity being mastered and the desire to control the personality position in the partnership. By the method of collaborative activity, it is necessary to understand the system of joint actions of the teacher and the student. Such a movement begins with the teacher's help to the student; the student's activity gradually grows to become a practical and mental movement entirely guided by them, while the communication between the teacher and the student becomes a partnership position characteristic.

REFERENCES

1. Дилова Н.Ф. (2017). Ўқувчи шахсини ривожлантиришда ҳамкорлик педагогикасининг ўрни. *Замонавий таълим*. 1-сон.
2. Rasulova Z.D. (2020). Pedagogical peculiarities of developing socio-perceptive competence in learners. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences*. 8:1, pp. 30-34.
3. Кулиева Ш.Х., Расулова З.Д. (2016). Формирование профессиональнопедагогической компетентности будущих специалистов на основе информационных технологий. *Молодой учёный*, №8 (112), С. 977-978.
4. Расулова З.Д. (2020). Дидактические основы развития у будущих учителей креативного мышления. *European science*, vol. 51, no. 2-2, pp. 65-68.
5. Dilova N.G. (2015). Situation of cooperation and the problems solved in it. *Образование через всю жизнь: непрерывное образование в интересах устойчивого развития*. 2: 13, pp. 102-103.
6. Расулова З.Д. (2018). Значения обучающих технологий направленной личности на уроках трудового обучения. *Ученые XXI века*, Т. 47, № 12, С. 34-35.
7. Rasulova Z.D. (2020). Conditions and opportunities of organizing independent creative works of students of the direction Technology in Higher Education. *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research*. 9:3, pp. 2552-2155.
8. Кулиева Ш.Х., Расулова З.Д. (2016). Инновационная деятельность педагога в образовании. *Молодой учёный*, № 8 (112), С. 978-979.

9. Аноркулова Г.М., Кулиева Ш.Х., Расулова З.Д. (2015). Методологические основы системного подхода при подготовке учителей профессионального обучения. Молодой учёный, 93:13, С. 588-590.
10. Аноркулова Г.М., Кулиева Ш.Х., Расулова З.Д. (2015). Модель подготовки учителей профессионального образования на основе системного подхода. Молодой учёный, 93:13, С. 590-592.
11. Дилова Н.Г. (2014). Значение процесса педагогического сотрудничества в формировании личности учащихся начальных классов. Сборники конференций НИЦ Социосфера. № 26, С. 190-193.
12. Кулиева Ш.Х., Хамроева Х.Ю., Расулова З.Д. (2013). Учебный процесс как педагогическая система в процессе подготовки учителей профессионального обучения. Молодой учёный, 56:9, С. 383-385.
13. Каххоров С.К., Расулова З.Д. (2020). Роль дистанционного обучения а развитии творческих навыков студентов. Проблемы педагогики. 49:4, С. 26-29.
14. Каххоров С.К., Расулова З.Д. (2020). Компьютерные технологии обучения как важный фактор для улучшения процесса преподавания. Современные инновации. 36:2, С. 44-46. SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS VOLUME 2 | ISSUE 6 | 2021 ISSN: 2181-1601 Uzbekistan www.scientificprogress.uz Page 971
15. Kakhkhorov S.K., Rasulova Z.D. (2020). Methodology of improving the professional activity of the future teacher of technology on the basis of modern educational technologies. Universal J. of Educational Research. 8:12, pp. 7006-7014.
16. Расулова З.Д., Содикова А.Х. (2020). Возможности использования компьютерных технологий в технологическом образовании. Вестник науки и образования. 19 (97), часть 2, С. 68-71.
17. Дилова Н.Г. (2013). Требования к учителю по организации сотрудничества учащихся начальных классов в учебном процессе. Актуальные проблемы современной науки. № 4 (72). С. 55-57.
18. Расулова З.Д. (2020). Эффективность дистанционной организации процессов обучения в высшем образовании. Academy. 62:11, С. 31-34.
19. Каримова М.Н., Расулова З.Д. (2020). Использование учебных инструментов в развитии творческого мышления учащихся. Проблемы педагогики, № 5 (50), С. 19-22.
20. Расулова З.Д. (2020). Наука и образование в период пандемии. Наука, техника и образование. № 11 (75), С. 101-104.
21. Rasulov T.H., Rasulova Z.D. (2019). Organizing educational activities based on interactive methods on mathematics subject. Journal of Global Research in Mathematical Archives, 6:10, pp. 43-45.
22. Расулова З.Д. (2021). Технологии развития творческих способностей будущего учителя. Наука, техника и образование. 77:2-1, С. 34-37.
23. Расулова З.Д. (2021). Роль электронного учебно-методического комплекса в оптимизации учебных процессов. Academy. № 3 (66), С. 27-30.
24. Расулова З.Д. (2021). Технологии развития творческих качеств студентов. Наука и образования сегодня. 60:1, С. 34-37.

25. Расулова З.Д. (2020). Программные инструменты - важный фактор развития творчества учащихся. Вестник науки и образования. № 21 (99), часть 2, С. 37-40.
26. Rasulova Z.D. (2014). Investigations of the essential spectrum of a model operator associated to a system of three particles on a lattice. J. Pure and App. Math.: Adv. Appl., 11:1, pp. 37-41.
27. Rasulova Z.D. (2014). On the spectrum of a three-particle model operator. Journal of Mathematical Sciences: Advances and Applications, 25, pp. 57-61.
28. Расулова З.Д., Хамроева Х.Ю. (2014). Числовой образ модели Фридрикса с одномерным возмущением. Молодой учёный. 61 (7), С. 27-29.
29. Расулова З.Д., Хамроева Х.Ю. (2014). Number and location of the eigenvalues of a 2x2 operator matrix. Молодой учёный. 66 (7), С. 7-9.
30. Dilova N.G., Saidova M.J. (2020). Formative assessment of students' knowledge as an innovative approach to education. The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations. 2:12, P. 190-19